

UTILIZATION OF FECAL OCCULT BLOOD TEST DONE AS A SCREENING TOOL FOR COLORECTAL CANCER IN HEALTH CARE SPECIALTY CENTER – KAMC, RIYADH IN 2026

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ABSTRACT

Background: Fecal occult blood testing (FOBT) is a widely used, non-invasive screening tool for detecting gastrointestinal bleeding and colorectal cancer (CRC). The test is commonly performed in primary care and hospital settings to identify early signs of disease, thereby improving patient outcomes. Understanding the demographic characteristics and distribution of FOBT positivity rates can help optimize screening programs and improve early detection strategies. This study aimed to analyze the demographic factors, departmental distribution, and positivity rates of FOBT among patients visiting primary health care in king Abdulaziz medical city KAMC in 2026.

Methodology: This retrospective observational study analyzed data from 90,661 patients visiting primary health care in king Abdulaziz medical city KAMC in 2026. Among these, 3955 (4.4%) patients underwent FOBT. Patient demographic data, including age, gender, nationality, marital status, and visit type, were collected. The distribution of FOBT across different medical departments was examined, and positivity rates were calculated.

Statistical analyses were conducted to assess the association between demographic factors and FOBT results.

Results: The mean age of patients undergoing FOBT was 59.12 years (SD= 7.41), with a female predominance (55.2%). Saudi nationals accounted for 99.2% of the tested patients. The majority of FOBTs were conducted in the Family Medicine department (86.8%), followed by the Satellite Emergency Department (10.3%). Overall, 96.3% of FOBT results were negative, while 3.7% were positive. Males had a significantly higher positivity rate (4.4%) compared to females (3.0%) ($p = 0.001$). However, no significant associations were observed between FOBT positivity and other demographic factors such as age, nationality, marital status, or visit type. Monthly trends in FOBT testing showed fluctuations, with peaks in October and November.

Conclusion: This study highlights the demographic characteristics and distribution of FOBT testing among hospitalized patients in Saudi Arabia. The significant association between male gender and positive FOBT results suggests the need for targeted screening strategies. The findings reinforce the role of primary care settings in preventive screening and emphasize the importance of optimizing FOBT utilization.

KEYWORDS

Fecal Occult Blood Test, Screening, Colorectal Cancer

INTRODUCTION

Colorectal cancer (CRC) is major health issue worldwide, it is one of most common form of cancer after lung and breast cancer and the fourth of causing cancer death [1]. The lifetime probability of developing CRC is 5.5% in men and 5.1% in women [2]. In Saudi Arabia, the most common cancer in Saudi males is colorectal cancer and considered to be the third in Saudi female [3]. CRC mortality rate depend up on many verities including stage at diagnosis, resources and it is usually higher in developed country [2].

Risk factors for CRC including men gender, advanced age, sedentary lifestyle, physical inactivity, obesity, high in red meat, smoking, Inflammatory bowel diseases and positive family history of CRC [4]. Survival rate of CRC improved from 58% to 61.3% secondary to advances in diagnosis, treatment of CRC and to introduction of CRC screening [4]. If

CRC is detected by appearing of symptoms the disease usually well developed with high mortality rate 40-50% [4]. In Saudi Arabia, late diagnosis of CRC considered to be a concern as 58 years old is the mean age for diagnosis and usually patient get diagnosed over 45 years old. So, about 25% will be presented with distant metastasis and only 23% will have localized disease [5]. The U.S. Preventive Services Task Force (Task Force) recommends that adults age 45 to 75 be screened for colorectal cancer [6].

There are many types of CRC screening tools, most CRC screening test designed to detect tiny trace of blood in stool like Fecal occult blood test (FOBT) which performed every one to two years, other screening method use direct visualization techniques, such as colonoscopy every ten years and flexible sigmoidoscopy every five years, a few use image techniques such as computed tomography (CT), colonography and rarely use capsule endoscopy or double -contrast barium enema and x-ray examination of the bowel [5]. FOBT screening cannot distinguish between upper and lower Gastrointestinal bleeding and test result may be affected by oral intake. however, FOBT is cheap and easy to apply [2].

Study done in Saudi Arabia, showed deficits in public CRC knowledge and their awareness of preventative measures. These deficiencies were found to be mainly related to education level [7]. Colorectal cancer screening utilization was low in Saudi Arabia as per study done in 2018 which revealed only 5.64% [8]. The goal of this study is to measure the utilization of FOBT screening for CRC in our hospital (king Abdelaziz Medical City) in 2026 of age group 45 to 75 years old.

METHODOLOGY

This study was a quantitative observational retrospective cross-sectional study conducted using the medical record numbers (MRN) of adult patients aged 45–75 years who had visited King Abdulaziz Medical City, Health Care Specialty Center (HCSC), Riyadh, Saudi Arabia, during the year 2026. A structured data collection form was designed to extract relevant information from medical records.

The study was conducted at King Abdulaziz Medical City, specifically within the Health Care Specialty Center (HCSC) in Riyadh. HCSC is a specialized medical facility that provides healthcare services primarily to National Guard personnel, their dependents, and other eligible patients within the designated catchment area, including the Eastern region of Riyadh. The center has expanded its services significantly, with an estimated 21,737 patient visits per month, making it a suitable setting for this study.

The study included adult patients aged 45–75 years who had follow-up visits at HCSC-KAMC during the years 2026. The inclusion criteria included adult patients aged 45–75 years who had a follow-up visit at HCSC-KAMC in 2026. Patients with contraindications for fecal occult blood testing (FOBT), those who provided fewer than three FOBT samples, and those with incomplete or insufficient medical records were excluded.

The sample size was estimated using the OpenEpi calculator, assuming a total population size of 1,000,000. The final sample size was determined based on statistical considerations to ensure adequate representation and power for analysis. Since the study population was limited, all patients who met the inclusion criteria were included in the study without random sampling.

A structured record form was developed based on an extensive literature review. The form consisted of two main sections: the first part included demographic information such as age and gender, while the second part focused on clinical factors related to medical history and assessments relevant to the study. To ensure content validity, the record form was reviewed and finalized by two experts in the field. Data extraction from medical records was performed systematically to maintain accuracy and consistency.

Data were initially entered into Microsoft Excel for organization and quality control. After verification, the data were transferred and analyzed using SPSS version 21. Descriptive statistics were used to summarize the data, with categorical variables such as gender reported as frequencies and percentages, while numerical variables such as age were summarized using mean and standard deviation. Chi-square test was used to compare categorical data such as gender, while a correlation coefficient analysis was conducted to assess the relationship between quantitative variables such as age. A p-value of less than 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

RESULTS

A total of 90,655 patients visited to hospitals during the study period 2026, among whom 3955 patients underwent 7954 fecal occult blood testing (FOB). The demographic characteristics of these patients are presented in Table 1. The majority of tests were conducted from Khashm Alan Clinic (51.8%), followed by Um Alhamam Clinic (22.3%) and Iskan Yarmouk (17.0%). The mean age of the patients was 59.12 years (SD = 7.41), with all patients residing in the central region. Male patients constituted 44.8% of the sample, while female patients accounted for 55.2%. The overwhelming majority of patients were Saudi nationals (99.2%), with only 0.8% being non-Saudi. Regarding

marital status, most patients were married (89.1%), while smaller proportions were widowed (7.0%), single (1.7%), divorced (1.5%), or had unknown marital status (0.7%). Most visits were first visits (94.9%), whereas follow-up visits accounted for 5.1% of the cases. Moreover, 40.1 % of the total visits were reported in 2026 with 54.8 % of the patients make a one visit, while 33.2 % conducted FOBT for three times or more (Table 1).

Table 1: Demographic factors of patients underwent FOB

		Count	Column N %
Facility name (No. Of visits)	Um Alhamam Clinic	1774	22.3%
	Khashm Alan Clinic	4124	51.8%
	PRINCE BADER RESIDENTAL CITY CLINIC (PBRCC)	92	1.2%
	Iskan Yarmouk	1356	17.0%
	King Saud City (Dirab)	320	4.0%
	Riyadh Dialysis South Center	167	2.1%
	Ministry Of National Guard Clinic	17	0.2%
	Hail Clinic	36	0.5%
	Riyadh Dialysis North Center	55	0.7%
	Battalion and Brigade Clinic	12	0.2%
	King Khalid Military Academy Clinic	1	0.0%
Age	Mean (SD)	59.12 (7.41)	
Gender	Male	1772	44.8%
	Female	2183	55.2%
Nationality	Non-Saudi	33	0.8%
	Saudi	3922	99.2%
Marital status	Unknown	27	0.7%
	Single	68	1.7%
	Married	3524	89.1%
	Divorced	61	1.5%
	Widow	275	7.0%
Visit	FV	203	5.1%
	FU	3752	94.9%

Frequency of visit by patient in 2026	One visit	971	54.8%
	Two visit	213	12.0%
	3 or more visit	588	33.2%
	Total visits	3191	
Frequency of visit by patient in 2026	One visit	1062	44.9%
	Two visit	313	13.2%
	3 or more visit	990	41.9%
	Total visits	4763	

The incidence of FOB testing across different months in 2026 is illustrated in Figure 1. The number of FOB tests fluctuated over time, with noticeable peaks and declines. In 2026, the highest number of tests was recorded in December (402), followed by October (350) and November (338). The lowest testing frequency was observed in April (164) and July (158). In 2026, the number of tests was generally higher than in the previous year, with peaks in October (619), November (529), and June (449). The lowest number of tests was recorded in April (118), which was consistent with the seasonal decline observed in the previous year.

Figure 1: The incidence of applied FOB by months and years

Regarding the distribution of FOB tests across different medical departments, as shown in Table 2, the majority of tests were ordered by the Family Medicine department (86.8%), followed by the Satellite Emergency Department (10.3%). Other departments contributed minimally to the total number of FOB tests, including Nephrology (2.8%), Emergency Medicine (0.1%), Internal Medicine (0.0%), Obstetrics and Gynecology (0.0%), Pediatrics (0.0%), and Dermatology (0.0%). The results of the FOB tests indicated that 96.3% of patients had a negative result, while 3.7% tested positive.

Table 2: FOB results

		Count	Column N %
Department	Family medicine	6905	86.8%
	Satellite emergency department	816	10.3%
	Emergency Medicine	5	0.1%
	Nephrology	222	2.8%
	Internal Medicine	1	0.0%

	OB and GYN	3	0.0%
	Pediatric	1	0.0%
	Dermatology	1	0.0%
Results of FOB	Negative	7656	96.3%
	Positive	298	3.7%

Table 3 presents the relationship between FOB test results and demographic factors. The mean age was similar between patients with negative (59.28 ± 7.308) and positive (59.46 ± 7.499) FOB results, with no significant difference ($p = 0.681$). A significant association was found between gender and FOB test results ($p = 0.001$), with male patients having a higher proportion of positive FOB results (4.4%) compared to female patients (3.0%). No significant differences were observed based on nationality ($p = 0.450$), as both Saudi (3.8%) and non-Saudi (1.8%) patients had comparable rates of positive FOB results. Marital status also did not show a significant association with FOB outcomes ($p = 0.486$). Widowed patients had the highest percentage of positive FOB results (4.7%), while single, divorced, and married individuals had similar rates (3.6%–3.7%). The type of visit (first vs. follow-up) did not significantly impact FOB results ($p = 0.773$), with first-visit patients having a positive rate of 3.7% and follow-up patients showing a similar rate of 4.0%.

		Results of FOB				P-value
		Negative		Positive		
		Count	Row N %	Count	Row N %	
Age	Mean (SD)	59.28 (7.308)		59.46 (7.499)		0.681
Gender	Male	3998	95.6%	184	4.4%	0.001*
	Female	3658	97.0%	114	3.0%	
Nationality	Saudi	7602	96.2%	297	3.8%	0.450
	Non-Saudi	54	98.2%	1	1.8%	
Marital status	Unknown	68	93.2%	5	6.8%	0.486
	Single	134	96.4%	5	3.6%	
	Married	6861	96.3%	260	3.7%	
	Divorced	107	96.4%	4	3.6%	

	Widow	486	95.3%	24	4.7%	
Visit	FV	7099	96.3%	275	3.7%	0.773
	FU	557	96.0%	23	4.0%	
Ferritin	Mean (SD)	145.04 (361.0)		126.26 (183.32)		0.374

DISCUSSION

The present study analyzed data from 90,655 patients visited PHC in KAMC in 2026, with 3955 (4.4%) undergoing fecal occult blood testing (FOBT). The mean age of these patients was 59.29 years, and the cohort consisted predominantly of female (55.2%) and Saudi nationals (99.3%). The majority of FOBTs were conducted in the Family Medicine department (86.8%), with a smaller proportion in the Satellite Emergency Department (10.3%). Notably, 96.3% of the FOBT results were negative, while 3.7% were positive.

The observed FOBT positivity rate of 3.7% aligns with findings from similar studies [9–11]. A study at a medical college and hospital in Saudi Arabia found a 20% positivity rate among 500 patients aged 40 and older [12]. In addition, another study showed that fecal occult blood tests have positive results about 1% to 16% of the time, depending on such factors as the age of the person being tested, whether the sample is rehydrated, and whether the test is used for initial screening or for rescreening [13]. These variations in positivity rates may be attributed to differences in study populations, screening protocols, and regional factors.

Gender differences in FOBT results were significant in our study, with males exhibiting a higher positivity rate (4.4%) compared to females (3.0%). This finding is consistent with previous research indicating that males are at a higher risk for colorectal cancer (CRC) and related pathologies [14–17]. However, no significant associations were found between FOBT results and other demographic factors such as age, nationality, marital status, or visit type. This suggests that while gender may influence FOBT outcomes, other demographic variables may not have a substantial impact. In the current study, most of the participants were in 50-59 age range which is consistent with the global recommendation to initiate routine screening for colon cancer at age 50 [18].

The distribution of FOBT across medical departments revealed that the Family Medicine department conducted the majority of tests (86.8%). This aligns with the role of primary care settings in preventive health measures, including CRC screening [19]. The relatively

lower percentage of tests conducted by other departments may reflect the structured pathways for CRC screening within the healthcare system.

Temporal analysis showed fluctuations in the number of FOBTs performed monthly, with peaks in October and November of both years. These trends could be influenced by various factors, including public health initiatives, seasonal variations in healthcare utilization, or the scheduling of routine screenings. Understanding these patterns is crucial for optimizing resource allocation and planning effective screening programs.

The findings of this study underscore the importance of targeted screening strategies, particularly focusing on high-risk groups such as males. The significant association between male gender and positive FOBT results highlights the need for increased awareness and potentially more aggressive screening protocols for this demographic. Additionally, the central role of the Family Medicine department in conducting FOBTs emphasizes the importance of primary care settings in early detection efforts.

In conclusion, this study provides valuable insights into the demographic factors associated with FOBT outcomes and the distribution of testing across medical departments. The findings highlight the need for targeted screening strategies and reinforce the pivotal role of primary care in preventive health measures. Future research should explore the underlying causes of gender disparities in FOBT positivity and assess the effectiveness of current screening protocols in different demographic groups.

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